

CORRIGENDUM TO: THE GENERAL *GCD*-PRODUCT FUNCTION

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Lemma 1 is incorrect. As a result the error terms for some of the estimates are slightly off. In particular, most of the error terms involving a $\log^2(x)$ should actually be $\log^3(x)$. Except for this slight change, the paper and the essence of the results are correct.

I sincerely thank Prof. J. Spilker for pointing out the error.

Explicitly the following needs to be changed:

1. Lemma 1: Change $\frac{\log(x)}{\log(y)}$ to $\frac{\log^2(x)}{4\log(y)}$.
2. Theorem 9: Change $O(x \log^2(x))$ to $O(x \log^3(x))$.
3. Corollary 6: Change $O(x^x \log(x))$ to $O(x^x \log^2(x))$.
4. Theorem 11: Change $O(x \log^2(x))$ to $O(x \log^3(x))$ and change $O(\log^2(x))$ to $O(\log^3(x))$.
5. Corollary 9: Change $O(x^x \log(x))$ to $O(x^x \log^2(x))$ and change $O(x^{\log(x)})$ to $O(x^{\log^2(x)})$.

Due to these errors, I recreate and clarify the proofs of the Lemma 1, Theorem 9 and Theorem 11 in the following pages.

Lemma 1. If x and y are real numbers such that $x \geq y > 1$, then

$$0 \leq \log\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) \leq \frac{\log^2(x)}{4\log(y)}.$$

Proof. Fix $x > 1$ and consider the function $a_x(y) = \log(y) \log\left(\frac{x}{y}\right)$ on the domain $[1, x]$. Taking the derivative with respect to y gives

$$a'_x(y) = \frac{\log(x)}{y} - 2\frac{\log(y)}{y} = \frac{1}{y} [\log(x) - 2\log(y)].$$

Thus, $a_x(y)$ attains a maximum when $\log(x) - 2\log(y) = 0$, that is, $y = \sqrt{x}$ (Note that $a'_x(y) > 0$ for $1 \leq y < \sqrt{x}$ and $a'_x(y) < 0$ for $\sqrt{x} < y \leq x$). Therefore, for $y \in [1, x]$, we have

$$a_x(y) = \log(y) \log\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) \leq \log(\sqrt{x}) \log\left(\frac{x}{\sqrt{x}}\right) = \frac{1}{4} \log^2(x).$$

Thus, $\log\left(\frac{x}{y}\right) \leq \frac{\log^2(x)}{4\log(y)}$ for $1 < y \leq x$. □

Note the estimates $\Phi_0(x) := \sum_{n \leq x} \phi(n) = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} + O(x \log(x))$ and $\Phi_1(x) := \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\phi(n)}{n} = \sum_{n \leq x} \frac{\phi(n)}{n} = \frac{x}{\zeta(2)} + O(\log(x))$.

Theorem 9. If $h(x)$ satisfies the relationship $h(n) = O(n^\alpha)$ for n sufficiently large and α a fixed non-negative real number, then the following asymptotic relationship holds

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log[g(n; h)] = \frac{H_h}{2\zeta(2)} x^2 + O(x \log^3(x)) \text{ for } x \text{ sufficiently large,}$$

where $H_h = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log[h(k)]}{k^2}$.

Proof. From Theorem 6, observe that $\sum_{n \leq x} \log[g(n; h)] = \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{d|n} \log(h(d)) \phi(n/d) = \sum_{d \leq x} \log(h(d)) \sum_{e \leq x/d} \frac{\phi(e)}{e} = \sum_{d \leq x} \log(h(d)) \Phi_0(x/d)$. Using the estimate for $\Phi_0(x)$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log[g(n; h)] = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(h(d))}{d^2} + O\left(x \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(h(d))}{d} \log(x/d)\right)$$

The main term simplifies as

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(h(d))}{d^2} &= \frac{x^2}{\zeta(2)} \left[H_h - \sum_{d > x} \frac{\log(h(d))}{d^2} \right] \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \left[H_h - O\left(\sum_{d > x} \frac{\alpha \log(d)}{d^2}\right) \right] \text{ (since } h(n) = O(n^\alpha) \text{)} \\ &= \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \left[H_h - O\left(\int_x^\infty \frac{\log(x)}{x^2} dx\right) \right] = \frac{x^2}{2\zeta(2)} \left[H_h - O\left(\frac{\log(x)}{x}\right) \right] \\ &= \frac{x^2 H_h}{2\zeta(2)} + O(x \log(x)). \end{aligned}$$

Using Lemma 1, the error term becomes

$$\begin{aligned} x \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(h(d))}{d} \log(x/d) &= O\left(x \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(h(d)) \log^2(x)}{d \cdot 4\log(d)}\right) \\ &= O\left(x \log^2(x) \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{1}{d}\right) \text{ (since } h(n) = O(n^\alpha) \text{)} \\ &= O\left(x \log^3(x)\right). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\sum_{n \leq x} \log[g(n)] = \frac{x H_h}{2\zeta(2)} + O(x \log(x)) + O(x \log^3(x)) = \frac{x H_h}{2\zeta(2)} + O(x \log^3(x))$. □

Theorem 11. The following asymptotic relationships hold

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log[g(n)] = -\frac{\zeta'(2)}{2\zeta(2)}x^2 + O(x \log^3(x)) \text{ for } x \text{ sufficiently large, and}$$

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log[f(n)] = -\frac{\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)}x + O(\log^3(x)) \text{ for } x \text{ sufficiently large.}$$

Proof. Using Theorem 9 with $e(x) = x$, we have $H_e = \sum_{k=1}^{\infty} \frac{\log(k)}{k^2} = -\zeta'(2)$. This gives the result for $\log[g(n)]$. Since $f(n) = g(n)^{1/n}$, note that $\log[f(n)] = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{d|n} \phi(n/d) \log(d) = \sum_{d|n} \frac{\phi(n/d) \log(d)}{n/d}$. Thus $\sum_{n \leq x} \log[f(n)] = \sum_{n \leq x} \sum_{d|n} \frac{\log(d) \phi(n/d)}{d} \frac{n/d}{n/d} = \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d} \sum_{e \leq x/d} \frac{\phi(e)}{e} = \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d} \Phi_1(x/d)$. Using the estimate for $\Phi_1(x)$, we have

$$\sum_{n \leq x} \log[f(n)] = \frac{x}{\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d^2} + O\left(\sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d} \log(x/d)\right)$$

Using the same technique as in Theorem 9, the main term simplifies as

$$\frac{x}{\zeta(2)} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d^2} = -\frac{x\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} + O(\log(x)).$$

Using Lemma 1, the error term becomes

$$\begin{aligned} \sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d)}{d} \log(x/d) &= O\left(\sum_{d \leq x} \frac{\log(d) \log^2(x)}{d \cdot 4 \log(d)}\right) \\ &= O(\log^3(x)). \end{aligned}$$

Hence, $\sum_{n \leq x} \log[f(n)] = -\frac{x\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} + O(\log(x)) + O(\log^3(x)) = -\frac{x\zeta'(2)}{\zeta(2)} + O(\log^3(x))$. \square